

STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF THALLIUM FERROCYANIDE BY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS

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The composition of thallium ferrocyanide has been studied by conductometric, potentiometric and thermometric titrations at several dilutions of the reactants, potassium ferrocyanide and thallium nitrate. The composition of the complex agrees with the formula $Tl_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2H_2O$.

Flecher and Benziar (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1902, 26, 49) observed that a yellow crystalline compound, $Tl_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2H_2O$ was obtained, when hot concentrated solution of thalious sulphate was added to potassium ferrocyanide solution and the mixture allowed to cool. The crystalline precipitate was sparingly soluble in cold, but more readily in hot water. In order to study the composition of the precipitated compound by physico-chemical methods, conductometric, potentiometric and thermometric titrations were performed at different dilutions and molar concentrations of the reactants. The composition, determined by the above mentioned methods in aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic solutions, has been reported in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Thallium nitrate (Merck's guaranteed reagent) was dissolved in conductivity water, and thallium estimated as Tl_2CrO_4 (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 564). Potassium ferrocyanide was estimated as described in our previous publication (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 473). Determinations of conductivity and the measurement of E.M.F. were carried out as described earlier (*ibid.*, 1953, 30, 158, 163). The results of the conductometric and thermometric titrations of thallium ferrocyanide are recorded in Table I, and potentiometric measurements in Table II.

TABLE I
 $M/5-K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and $M/5-TlNO_3$.
Conc ratio (n) = 1 : 1.

† $M/5-TlNO_3$ (V).	Alcohol added.	$M/5-K_4Fe(CN)_6$ required for V c.c. of $M/5-TlNO_3$ (V_1 c.c.)	$M/5-K_4Fe(CN)_6$ calc. for 10 c.c. of $M/5-TlNO_3$ ($(V_1/V) \times 10$).	Compound formed.	Curve No.
Conductometric.					
* 10 c.c.	0 c.c.	2.2 c.c.	2.20 c.c.	$Tl_4Fe(CN)_6$	1
9	1	2.1	2.32	Do	2
8	2	2.0	2.50	Do	3
Thermometric.					
20	0	4.0	{ 4.0		4
18	2	3.7	{ 4.10		5
16	4	3.4	{ 4.25		6

† For conductometric method $TlNO_3$ was taken in the cell and for thermometric study, in a Dewar flask.

* Calc. titre value for 10 c.c. of $M/5-TlNO_3$ for the formation of the compound $Tl_4Fe(CN)_6$ is 2.50 c.c. of $M/5-K_4Fe(CN)_6$

** For 20 c.c. of $M/5-TlNO_3$.

TABLE II

$M/5\text{-TiNO}_3$	Alcohol added.	Range for maximum change in DE/dc .		Curve No.
20 c.c.	0 c.c.	4.0	to 4.2	7
18	2	3.6	" 3.8	8
16	4	3.2	" 3.4	9

At the equivalence point the curve did not show a steep fall. The value of DE/dc became maximum in the vicinity of the equivalence point.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

It was observed that the behaviour of thallium ferrocyanide was unlike that of the insoluble complexes of uranyl and thorium ferrocyanides, communicated previously (this *Journal*, 1953, 39, 159; 1954, 31, 467). A little or no precipitate was formed when dilute solutions were mixed; the precipitated complex was definitely crystalline. It was partly soluble in excess of water, more in hot than in cold; it could, however, be almost quantitatively precipitated by mixing $M/5$ solutions of the reactants and of higher concentrations. Since the precipitate would dissolve in excess of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, it was only possible to perform the conductivity titrations by taking the thallium nitrate in the conductivity cell and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in the burette.

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When the titrations were carried out in aqueous medium, the observed titre values were slightly less than the calculated equivalent (vide table & curves), but in a queous alcoholic medium the titre approached the equivalent amount; the formula $Tl_4Fe(CN)_6$ for the precipitate was in agreement with the titre obtained in presence of 20% alcohol by conductometry, and the titre equivalents of thermometric curves were only in fair agre ement with the conductometric result. The potentiometric curves did not show a very steep fall and, hence, more divergence from the theoretical value was observed.

The low values of the titre in aqueous solutions follow from the solubility of the crystalline precipitate. An equilibrium

exists near the end-point, which is responsible for the discrepancies observed.

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